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Effects Of Cultural Values And Emotional Intelligence On Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the impact of cultural values and emotional intelligence levels of private sector employees in Northern Cyprus (KKTC) on job satisfaction. The study's population consists of private sector employees aged 18 to 65 in KKTC. A total of 306 individuals were included in the study using a randomized sampling method. A questionnaire consisting of five sections was used as the data collection tool. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 26.0 software was used for data analysis. The study found negative and significant correlations between the participants' scores on the Power Distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and their scores on the overall Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, as well as the internal and external satisfaction sub-dimensions. Furthermore, positive and significant correlations were found between the participants' scores on the Uncertainty Avoidance, Collectivism, and Long-Term Orientation sub-dimensions of the Cultural Values Scale and their scores on the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, indicating that higher scores on these cultural values were associated with higher job satisfaction. The study did not find any significant correlations between the participants' scores on the Masculinity sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and their scores on the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Additionally, the study found positive correlations between the participants' scores on the Emotional Intelligence Scale, particularly on the sub-dimensions related to awareness of emotions, awareness of others' emotions, emotional use, and emotional regulation, and their scores on the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. This suggests that higher emotional intelligence is associated with higher job satisfaction. In this context, emphasizing the importance of teaching and developing emotional intelligence competencies in organizations to enhance job satisfaction is crucial. It also suggests that evolving cultural values in a way that promotes job satisfaction is essential for both organizations and employees' productivity. However, it is important to note that the study has certain limitations, such as a relatively small sample size and the reliance on self-reported questionnaire responses. Further research with larger and more diverse samples may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the relationships between cultural values, emotional intelligence, and job satisfaction.

Keywords: Culture, cultural values, intelligence, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction

1. INTRODUCTION

With the technological advancements and globalization witnessed today, organizations have started operating in different cultural environments beyond their boundaries. This has led to the emergence of multinational corporations operating in diverse cultural contexts. All these developments have highlighted the importance of intercultural differences in various aspects of life, including the workplace. As a result of the new world order and globalization, intercultural interactions and exchanges have become prominent, making the concept of cultural intelligence highly relevant. Human beings, inherently composed of biological, social, and cultural dimensions, are recognized as bio-cultural and social beings (Demirel and Kaya, 2006).

As a result of the technological advancements, various changes are occurring in cultural and social structures. These changes affect not only individuals but also many different areas of life, including the work environment, where individuals are considered as fundamental building blocks. The structures formed when individuals come together evaluate not only their cognitive attributes but also their social and cultural dimensions and characteristics. As institutions globalize and the workforce diversifies, it is observed that in some fields and under different circumstances, some individuals work more efficiently in emotional and cultural dimensions compared to others. Therefore, the linkage of emotional, social, and cultural dimensions with the concept of intelligence has become a necessity in the changing world order.

The initial studies on the concept of intelligence evaluated it solely as the ability to understand concepts and solve problems in academic settings, but later studies revealed that this definition had become outdated, and intelligence could also manifest itself in non-academic contexts. With the acceleration of studies on this subject, different types of intelligences, such as emotional intelligence, cultural intelligence, cognitive intelligence, social intelligence, and practical intelligence, began to be discussed (Early and Ang, 2003).

Studies on cultural intelligence aim to explain how some individuals may be more successful in different situations and environments in terms of cultural characteristics, while others may be less successful and less efficient in similar situations and environments. Cultural intelligence, defined as an individual's ability or skill to perform effectively and efficiently in different environments with different cultural characteristics, is similar to the general intelligence definition, which is described as the ability to understand and express problems accurately (Schmidt, Oh, and Hayes, 2009). The concept of cultural intelligence, like other types of intelligence, is not fixed and unchangeable; it is described as a type of intelligence that can be developed to a certain extent, similar to emotional intelligence (Merican, 2016).

Individuals with different lifestyles have varying personal characteristics. Adapting to uncertainties and changing situations in the work environment is achieved more through emotional intelligence (EQ) than cognitive intelligence. People who understand those around them, can explain their current situation, make comparisons between events, and show empathy towards others are the ones who achieve success and happiness in their work life (Rockstuhl et al., 2011). In today's job recruitment processes, in addition to written exams, oral interviews are also conducted. Individuals with strong communication skills, who can express themselves clearly, know how to increase their motivation, have problem-solving skills, listen actively, and have high self-confidence, have an advantage in job interviews. Additionally, the ability to work harmoniously and efficiently with individuals with different cultural backgrounds is another crucial aspect that stands out in these evaluations. Therefore, carrying and developing the behaviors that form the basis of emotional and cultural intelligence is considered more important than having theoretical knowledge (Tanu and Sandeep, 2018).

In the field of social sciences, the concepts of emotional intelligence and cultural intelligence have been continuously researched, and their significance has been evaluated in various

contexts. Being aware of cultural values and influences among people is highly important, especially in understanding the processes in the workplace that reflect these cultural values. Therefore, it is essential to examine whether cultural intelligence can be shaped based on cultural structures and to evaluate the implications of emotional intelligence for both cultural diversity and job satisfaction (Somuncuoğlu, 2020). With globalization, the impact of cultural diversity in all parts of the world has emerged, and it has become necessary to examine its reflections in the Northern Cyprus, a small island country with diverse cultural features. In this context, the aim of this study is to explore the relationship between private sector employees' cultural values and emotional intelligence while examining the impact of cultural values on emotional intelligence and job satisfaction.

2. LITERATURE

2.1 *The Concept of Culture*

The word "culture" has its origins in Latin, originally meaning to cultivate the land. Over time, however, its meaning has evolved, taking on a different significance (Smith, 2001). Culture is a phenomenon that encompasses the material, spiritual, and even intellectual characteristics of a society or its individuals. It defines their way of life, beliefs, traditions, fundamental values, and more when these elements come together (Van Dyne et al., 2012). Culture is a belief and justice system constructed by a group of people within their own world (Tay and Chia, 2008). Culture exerts its influence in every corner of society and plays a significant role in shaping individuals' emotional, intellectual, and behavioral patterns.

The concept of culture is a comprehensive one, encompassing individuals' historical past, future, production, consumption, art, morality, traditions, and similar customs (Berberoğlu, 1990).

2.2 *Cultural Values*

All the concepts that constitute culture make up cultural values. Cultural values are of vital importance, ensuring individuals' moral comfort and harmonious coexistence. These values shape individuals according to their society. Values are societal beliefs, and individuals with the same culture respond to similar events in comparable ways. Cultural values are the shared convictions of society and come together with common emotions. They constitute the entirety of material and spiritual elements that encompass a society (Gül, 2013). Cultural values encompass individuals' purposes in life, their perspectives on the world, their languages, speech patterns, how they assess concepts of good and bad, right and wrong, their relationships with one another, their value judgments, responsibilities, attitudes, behaviors, beliefs, and societal interests (Koçel, 2013).

2.3 *Emotional Intelligence Concept*

Emotional intelligence is the ability to understand and distinguish one's own and the emotions of the people around them, and to use this knowledge in their thoughts and actions (Mayer and Salovey, 1990). Emotional intelligence is an intellectual skill and an art of managing emotions. It enables individuals to have a creative mindset by affecting them mentally. It enhances the ability of individuals to control their desires, emotions, and thoughts, ultimately increasing their intellectual power (Crowne et al., 2011).

One of the concepts that best embodies emotional intelligence is empathy. Communication skills, the ability to put oneself in someone else's shoes, and environmental awareness form the cornerstones of empathy. Emotional intelligence has been studied from various perspectives over the years. Research is ongoing regarding whether emotional intelligence is learned or inherited. Some studies suggest a genetic component, but Goleman asserts that emotional intelligence increases with age and is something that can be developed. Gardner, introducing the theory of multiple intelligences, added the concept of emotional intelligence, demonstrating

that intelligence is not one-dimensional (cited in Altan, 1999). Furthermore, Mayer and Salovey have defined emotional intelligence as the ability to perceive, evaluate, integrate emotions with thoughts, make judgments when necessary, and manage and regulate emotions. Goleman, on the other hand, describes it as the ability to recognize one's own emotions, understand the emotions of others, and manage relationships with both oneself and other individuals (cited in Doğan and Şahin, 2007).

Cooper and Sawaf expressed it as the ability to harness the power of emotions and effectively use human energy. This concept has gained attention, especially in organizational life, due to its positive effects. Nowadays, the idea of managing emotions, understanding others for a harmonious life and work life has brought emotional intelligence to the forefront. Emotional intelligence now surpasses cognitive intelligence and is considered in personnel selection (cited in Dağlı, 2006).

2.4. Job Satisfaction

Work occupies a significant portion of people's lives, especially as they reach a certain age. While work mainly serves the purpose of meeting individuals' material needs, it also significantly influences their personalities and psychological state. Job satisfaction characterizes individuals' psychological health and comfort, encompassing their thoughts and attitudes regarding their profession. It reflects the pleasant feelings individuals have towards their careers and workplaces. Job satisfaction relates to various social parameters regarding individuals' careers and workplaces. Job satisfaction is a concept that encompasses the thoughts and attitudes of individuals towards their profession or workplace (Sladojevic et al., 2016). Job satisfaction can be divided into external and internal satisfaction. External job satisfaction is satisfaction acquired from the results of one's work, whereas internal job satisfaction relates to the satisfaction felt during the work process. Internal job satisfaction may include satisfaction from learning new activities related to one's work (Rehman et al., 2013).

3. METHOD

3.1. Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research method. The research design followed a Descriptive (Statistical) Survey approach. Descriptive survey is a method to identify the most suitable article to examine and analyze results for generalization to ensure the generalizability of results (Büyüköztürk, 2012).

3.2. Population and Sample

The population of this study consists of private sector employees in the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus (TRNC). A total of 306 private sector employees were included in the study using a random sampling method. The sample size was determined considering the total number of private sector employees in the TRNC. Data collection was completed between June 10, 2023, and August 10, 2023. The criteria for including individuals in the sample were working in any sector of the private sector at the time of the research, volunteering to participate in the study, and answering the research scales completely.

However, individuals who did not have an active work life and those working in public institutions were not included in the study. Before collecting data for the study, ethical approval was obtained from the Cyprus University of Health and Social Sciences Ethics Committee on May 8, 2023, with the reference number 2023/1008.

3.3. Data Collection

Prior to commencing data collection, the researcher informed the participants about the research's purpose, scope, and privacy boundaries. The questionnaire used in the research underwent a Turkish validity and reliability study conducted by Aydın Keleş (2018). The first section of the questionnaire includes a Socio-demographic Information Form consisting of six

questions related to participants' gender, age, marital status, monthly income level, and years of work experience.

The second section of the questionnaire employs the Cultural Values Scale. This scale, developed by Hofstede (1993) and validated by Boonghee Yoo and colleagues (2001), consists of a total of 26 items. It comprises five subscales: "Power Distance" (items 1-5), "Uncertainty Avoidance" (items 6-10), "Collectivism" (items 11-16), "Masculinity" (items 17-20), and "Long-Term Orientation" (items 21-26).

In the third section of the questionnaire, the Emotional Intelligence Scale developed by Wong and Law (2002) is employed. This scale consists of 16 items and is divided into four subscales: "Awareness of Own Emotions" (items 1-4), "Awareness of Others' Emotions" (items 5-8), "Use of Emotions" (items 9-12), and "Regulation of Emotions" (items 13-16).

The final section of the questionnaire uses the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Questionnaire, developed by Weiss, Dawis, England, and Lofquist (1967). This questionnaire measures participants' job satisfaction with two subscales: "Internal Satisfaction" (items 1-10) and "External Satisfaction" (items 11-20).

Table 1. Correlation and reliability analysis of the survey

	Ort	ST.	1	2	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1 Power distance	2,49	0,8311	1											
2 Uncertainty avoidance	4,023	0,7139	,116*	1										
3 Collectivism	3,614	0,8133	,133*	,398	1									
4 Masculinity	2,766	10,316	,223*	,181	,224	1								
5 Being long term oriented	4,214	0,5712	,099	,398	,362	,128	1							
6 Awareness of own emotions	3,991	0,6517	,094	,306	,206	-,010	,428	1						
7 Awareness of others emotions	4,056	0,6209	,043	,243	,268	,010	,432	,539	1					
8 Use of emotions	3,816	0,7292	,111*	,210	,205	,*63	,431	,476	,434	1				
9 Regulation of emotions	3,477	0,8692	-,025	,139	,159	,079	,300	,319	,309	,408	1			
10 Internal satisfaction	3,963	0,6939	,125*	,167	,227	,115	,412	,254	,329	,446	,208	1		
11 External satisfaction	3,68	0,7912	,108	,102	,244	,114	,353	,169	,294	,379	,212	,629	1	

**p<0,01

The Cronbach's Alpha coefficient was used for the reliability test. Reliability analysis examines the closeness of data and whether they have a homogeneous structure. Reliability is concerned with how accurately the questionnaire measures what it intends to measure. Its purpose is to determine whether the statements that make up the scale are homogeneous. In this study, except for the Power Distance dimension, all variables have a reliability coefficient equal to or greater than the threshold value of 0.70. This indicates that they have a homogeneous structure. Demonstrating a homogeneous structure in this way signifies that the scales are reliable. The coefficient that represents the linear relationship between two variables is called correlation.

The coefficient takes values between -1 and +1, and as its absolute value increases, the relationship between the variables strengthens. Approaching 0 indicates that there is no relationship between the two variables. Since $p < 0.01$, the correlation is significant. The table above provides the Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient and correlation coefficients for the scale.

3.4 Analysis of Data

Data analysis for the research was conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 25.0 software. The distribution of participants' socio-demographic characteristics was determined through frequency analysis. Descriptive statistics, such as mean, standard deviation, minimum, and maximum values, were provided for the scores obtained by the participants from the Cultural Values, Emotional Intelligence, and Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scales.

The fit of the participants' scores from the Cultural Values, Emotional Intelligence, and Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scales to a normal distribution was examined using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test and skewness-kurtosis values, and it was determined that they followed a normal distribution. Since scale scores conformed to a normal distribution, parametric hypothesis tests were used in the research. Pearson's test was employed to test the correlations between individuals' Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale scores and Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale scores. The situation of Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale scores in predicting Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale scores was examined through multivariate linear regression analysis.

4.RESULTS

Table 2. Socio-demographic characteristics of the participants

	Count (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Female	168	54,90
Male	138	45,10
Age		
25 years and below	38	12,42
26-35 years	81	26,47
36-45 years	106	34,64
46-55 years	67	21,90
56 years and above	14	4,58
Educational Status		
High School	105	34,31
Bachelor's Degree	144	47,06
Postgraduate	57	18,63
Relationship Status		
Single	135	44,12
Married	171	55,88
Income Status		
6.000 TL and below	115	37,58
6.001-8.000 TL	107	34,97
8.001-10.000 TL	55	17,97
10.0001 TL and above	29	9,48
Working Years		
5 years and below	73	23,86
6-10 years	79	25,82
11-15 years	78	25,49
16 years and above	76	24,84

In Table 2, it is observed that 12.42% of the participants were aged 25 and below, 26.47% were aged 26-35, 34.64% were aged 36-45, and 21.90% were aged 46-55. Regarding gender distribution, 54.90% were female, and 45.10% were male.

In terms of educational background, 34.31% had a high school education, 47.06% had a bachelor's degree, and 18.63% had a postgraduate degree. Marital status revealed that 44.12% were single, and 55.88% were married. Additionally, when it comes to monthly income, 37.58% of participants earned 6,000 TL or less, 34.97% earned between 6,001 and 8,000 TL, and 17.97% earned between 8,001 and 10,000 TL. Regarding their years of work experience, 23.86% had worked for 5 years or less, 25.82% for 6-10 years, 25.49% for 11-15 years, and 24.84% for 16 years and above.

Table 3. Participants' scores from the Cultural Values, Emotional Intelligence, Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

	n	\bar{x}	s	Min	Max
CVS - Power Distance	306	2,37	0,70	1,00	4,40
CVS - Uncertainty Avoidance	306	3,66	0,79	1,00	5,00
CVS - Collectivism	306	3,53	0,77	1,17	5,00
CVS - Masculinity	306	2,58	0,89	1,00	5,00
CVS – Being Long Term Oriented	306	3,79	0,73	1,33	5,00
EIS – Awareness of Own Emotions	306	3,74	0,81	1,00	5,00
EIS – Awareness of Others Emotions	306	3,81	0,77	1,25	5,00
EIS – Use of Emotions	306	3,65	0,82	1,25	5,00
EIS – Regulation of Emotions	306	3,55	0,80	1,00	5,00
MJS – Internal Satisfaction	306	3,76	0,66	1,92	5,00
MJS – External Satisfaction	306	3,56	0,75	1,00	5,00
Minnesota Job Satisfaction	306	3,66	0,63	1,79	5,00

In Table 3, it is determined that participants scored an average of 2.37 ± 0.70 points in the sub-dimension of power distance, 3.69 ± 0.79 points in the sub-dimension of uncertainty avoidance, 3.53 ± 0.77 points in the sub-dimension of collectivism, 2.58 ± 0.89 points in the sub-dimension of masculinity, and 3.79 ± 0.73 points in the sub-dimension of long-term orientation in the Cultural Values Scale.

Regarding the Emotional Intelligence Scale, participants scored an average of 3.74 ± 0.81 points in the sub-dimension of self-awareness of emotions, 3.81 ± 0.77 points in the sub-dimension of awareness of others' emotions, 3.65 ± 0.82 points in the sub-dimension of using emotions, and 3.55 ± 0.80 points in the sub-dimension of regulating emotions.

Participants obtained an average score of 3.66 ± 0.63 in the overall Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. In terms of sub-dimensions, they scored an average of 3.76 ± 0.66 points in the sub-dimension of internal satisfaction and 3.56 ± 0.75 points in the sub-dimension of external satisfaction.

Table 4. Correlations between participants' Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale scores and Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale scores

		Internal Satisfaction	External Satisfaction	Job Minnesota Satisfaction
	r	-0,369	-0,248	-0,340
CVS - Power Distance	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	0,551	0,349	0,494
CVS - Uncertainty Avoidance	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	0,584	0,465	0,580
CVS - Collectivism	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	-0,064	0,016	-0,024
CVS - Masculinity	p	0,262	0,784	0,672
	r	0,699	0,427	0,617
CVS – Being Long Term Oriented	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	0,571	0,380	0,523
EIS – Awareness of Own Emotions	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	0,659	0,414	0,589
EIS – Awareness of Others Emotions	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	0,619	0,499	0,619
EIS – Use of Emotions	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*
	r	0,488	0,452	0,522
EIS – Regulation of Emotions	p	0,000*	0,000*	0,000*

* $p < 0,05$

In Table 4, it has been determined that there are statistically significant and negative correlations ($p < 0.05$) between the scores obtained by private sector employees participating in the research from the power distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and the overall score of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, as well as the sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction. As the scores obtained from the power distance sub-dimension increase, the scores obtained from the overall Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale and its sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction decrease.

Furthermore, participants' scores from the sub-dimensions of uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, and long-term orientation in the Cultural Values Scale have shown statistically significant and positive correlations ($p < 0.05$) with the overall score of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, as well as the sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction. This implies that as the scores from the sub-dimensions of uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, and long-term orientation in the Cultural Values Scale increase, the scores obtained from the overall Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale and its sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction also increase.

However, there were no statistically significant correlations ($p > 0.05$) between the scores obtained by individuals participating in the research from the masculinity sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and the overall score of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, as well as its sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction.

Regarding the Emotional Intelligence Scale, it was observed that there are statistically significant and positive correlations ($p < 0.05$) between the scores obtained from the sub-dimensions of self-awareness of emotions, awareness of others' emotions, the use of emotions, and the regulation of emotions, and the overall score of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, as well as its sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction. This indicates that as the scores from the sub-dimensions of the Emotional Intelligence Scale increase, the scores obtained from the overall Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale and its sub-dimensions of internal satisfaction and external satisfaction also increase.

Table 5. Predictability of participants' Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale scores on Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale total scores

	Std. Olm. B	S.H.	Std Beta	t	p	F p	R ² DüzR ²
(Stable)	1,10	0,21		5,156	0,000*		
CVS - Power Distance	-0,12	0,04	-0,13	-3,070	0,002*		
CVS - Uncertainty Avoidance	0,05	0,04	0,06	1,317	0,189		
CVS - Collectivism	0,17	0,04	0,20	4,126	0,000*		
CVS - Masculinity	0,03	0,03	0,04	1,048	0,295	45,408	0,580
CVS – Being Long Term Oriented	0,12	0,05	0,14	2,473	0,014*	0,000*	0,567
EIS – Awareness of Own Emotions	-0,01	0,04	-0,01	-0,167	0,868		
EIS – Awareness of Others Emotions	0,13	0,05	0,16	2,954	0,003*		
EIS – Use of Emotions	0,15	0,04	0,20	3,592	0,000*		
EIS – Regulation of Emotions	0,13	0,04	0,16	3,403	0,001*		

* $p < 0,05$

Table 5 provides the results of the multivariate linear regression analysis, which examines the ability of the participants' scores from the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scales to predict the overall scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

Upon reviewing Table 5, it is evident that the scores obtained by participants from the power distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale negatively predict the overall scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale ($\beta = -0.13$; $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, the scores obtained by participants from the collectivism ($\beta = 0.20$; $p < 0.05$) and long-term orientation sub-dimensions ($\beta = 0.14$; $p < 0.05$) in the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predict the overall scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Additionally, the scores obtained by participants from the awareness of others' emotions ($\beta = 0.16$; $p < 0.05$), use of emotions ($\beta = 0.20$; $p < 0.05$), and regulation of emotions ($\beta = 0.16$; $p < 0.05$) sub-dimensions of the Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predict the overall scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. The model explains 56.7% of the variance. Therefore, an increase in the scores obtained from the power distance sub-dimension negatively affects the scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, while an increase in the scores from the collectivism, long-term orientation, awareness of others' emotions, use of emotions, and regulation of emotions sub-dimensions positively influences the scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

Table 6. Predictability of participants' Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale scores on Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale Intrinsic Satisfaction subscale scores

	Std. Olm.		Std	t	p	F	R ²
	B	S.H.	Beta				
(Stable)	0,91	0,21		4,446	0,000*		
CVS - Power Distance	-0,11	0,04	-0,11	-2,958	0,003*		
CVS - Uncertainty Avoidance	0,08	0,04	0,10	2,227	0,027*		
CVS - Collectivism	0,15	0,04	0,17	3,823	0,000*		
CVS - Masculinity	0,01	0,03	0,01	0,297	0,767	60,095	0,646
CVS – Being Long Term Oriented	0,22	0,05	0,24	4,536	0,000*	0,000*	0,636
EIS – Awareness of Own Emotions	0,02	0,04	0,02	0,400	0,690		
EIS – Awareness of Others Emotions	0,18	0,04	0,21	4,232	0,000*		
EIS – Use of Emotions	0,11	0,04	0,14	2,661	0,008*		
EIS – Regulation of Emotions	0,07	0,04	0,09	2,003	0,046*		

* $p < 0,05$

The results of the multivariate linear regression analysis, which examines the ability of the participants' scores from the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scales to predict the internal satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, are presented in Table 6. Upon reviewing Table 6, it is observed that the scores obtained by participants from the power distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale negatively predict the internal satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale ($\beta = -0.11$; $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, the scores obtained by participants from the collectivism ($\beta = 0.10$; $p < 0.05$) and long-term orientation sub-dimensions ($\beta = 0.17$; $p < 0.05$) in the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predict the internal satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Furthermore, the scores obtained by participants from the awareness of others' emotions ($\beta = 0.21$; $p < 0.05$), use of emotions ($\beta = 0.14$; $p < 0.05$), and regulation of emotions ($\beta = 0.09$; $p < 0.05$) sub-dimensions of the Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predict the internal satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. The model explains 63.6% of the variance. Therefore, an increase in the scores obtained from the power distance sub-dimension negatively affects the internal satisfaction scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, while an increase in the scores from the collectivism, long-term orientation, awareness of others' emotions, use of emotions, and regulation of emotions sub-dimensions positively influences the internal satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

Table 7. Predictability of participants' Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale scores on Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale Extrinsic Satisfaction subscale scores

	Std. Olm.		Std	t	p	F	R ²
	B	S.H.	Beta				
(Stable)	1,30	0,31		4,140	0,000*		
CVS - Power Distance	-0,12	0,06	-0,12	-2,261	0,024*		
CVS - Uncertainty Avoidance	0,02	0,06	0,02	0,342	0,732		
CVS - Collectivism	0,19	0,06	0,19	3,139	0,002*		
CVS - Masculinity	0,05	0,04	0,06	1,239	0,216	18,370	0,358
CVS – Being Long Term Oriented	0,03	0,07	0,03	0,409	0,683	0,000*	0,339
EIS – Awareness of Own Emotions	-0,03	0,06	-0,03	-0,491	0,624		
EIS – Awareness of Others Emotions	0,08	0,07	0,09	1,267	0,206		
EIS – Use of Emotions	0,20	0,06	0,22	3,170	0,002*		
EIS – Regulation of Emotions	0,18	0,05	0,19	3,343	0,001*		

* $p < 0,05$

Table 7 provides the results of the multivariate linear regression analysis, which examines the ability of the participants' scores from the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scales to predict the external satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

Upon reviewing Table 7, it is observed that the scores obtained by participants from the power distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale negatively predict the external satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale ($\beta=-0.12$; $p<0.05$). On the other hand, the scores obtained by participants from the collectivism sub-dimension ($\beta=0.19$; $p<0.05$) in the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predict the external satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

Furthermore, the scores obtained by participants from the use of emotions ($\beta=0.22$; $p<0.05$) and regulation of emotions ($\beta=0.19$; $p<0.05$) sub-dimensions of the Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predict the external satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. The model explains 33.9% of the variance. Therefore, an increase in the scores obtained from the power distance sub-dimension negatively affects the external satisfaction scores of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, while an increase in the scores from the collectivism, use of emotions, and regulation of emotions sub-dimensions positively influences the external satisfaction scores in the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

5. DISCUSSION, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study examines the impact of cultural values and emotional intelligence levels on job satisfaction among private sector employees in Northern Cyprus (KKTC).

In the study, it was found that there are negative and significant correlations between the scores participants received from the Power Distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and the general job satisfaction, as well as the internal and external satisfaction sub-dimensions of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

Additionally, participants' scores from the Uncertainty Avoidance, Collectivism, and Long-Term Orientation sub-dimensions of the Cultural Values Scale were positively and significantly correlated with the scores from the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

However, there was no significant correlation between the Masculinity sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and the job satisfaction dimensions.

These results suggest that different aspects of cultural values, such as power distance, uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, and long-term orientation, have varying effects on job satisfaction, while the masculinity dimension does not show a significant relationship with job satisfaction. Furthermore, in the study, it was determined that there are positive correlations between participants' scores from the Emotional Intelligence Scale's sub-dimensions of emotional awareness, awareness of others' emotions, use of emotions, and regulation of emotions, and the general job satisfaction as well as the internal and external satisfaction sub-dimensions of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Soares, Farhangmehr, and Shoham (2017) reported that high scores in the power distance sub-dimension negatively affect job satisfaction. In another study, it was found that participants who believed in the accuracy or appropriateness of the distribution of power in society had lower levels of job satisfaction compared to other participants. The study also indicated a relationship between cultural values such as uncertainty avoidance, collectivism, masculinity, and long-term orientation with job satisfaction, suggesting that as scores in these dimensions increased, job satisfaction levels also increased (Du Plessis, 2011). A study by Hair and colleagues (2010) examined the impact of cultural values on participants' job satisfaction and organizational commitment, revealing a relationship between the masculinity sub-dimension, which signifies the acceptance of money, individual goals, and wealth, and organizational commitment but not with job satisfaction. It was concluded that strong social relationships and quality of life were more determining factors in

job satisfaction. Additionally, Çıpa and colleagues (2021) reported that as individuals' emotional intelligence scores increased, their job satisfaction levels also increased. Aghdasi and colleagues (2011) proposed that individuals with high emotional intelligence would have their higher-level needs met when their lower-level needs are satisfied in the workplace, including needs related to salary, working conditions, job security, and respect, which would positively impact their internal and external satisfaction levels.

When examining the research findings, it was observed that participants' scores from the sub-dimension of power distance in the Cultural Values and Emotional Intelligence Scale negatively predicted the total scores on the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, while scores from the collectivism and long-term orientation sub-dimensions positively predicted the total scores on the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Furthermore, it was found that participants' scores from the sub-dimensions of awareness of others' emotions, use of emotions, and regulation of emotions in the Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predicted the total scores on the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. While there are supportive studies in the relevant literature (Kafetsios and Zampetakis, 2008; Levine, 2011; Orhan and Dinçer, 2012; Teli and Baba, 2017), there are also studies that yield different results (Craig and Douglas, 2016; Groves and Feyerherm, 2011). It is anticipated that this variation may be related to geographical differences. In this study, it was observed that participants' scores from the power distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and the Emotional Intelligence Scale negatively predicted the scores on the internal satisfaction sub-dimension of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, while scores from the collectivism and long-term orientation sub-dimensions positively predicted the scores on the internal satisfaction sub-dimension of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Additionally, it was found that participants' scores from the sub-dimensions of awareness of others' emotions, use of emotions, and regulation of emotions in the Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predicted the scores on the internal satisfaction sub-dimension of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale.

The relevant literature supports the findings of this study (Deconinck and Johnson, 2019; Fisher, 2011; Özaydın and Özdemir, 2014; Vurgun and Öztop, 2011).

In the study, it was found that participants' scores from the power distance sub-dimension of the Cultural Values Scale and the Emotional Intelligence Scale negatively predicted the scores on the external satisfaction sub-dimension of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale, while scores from the collectivism sub-dimension positively predicted the scores on the external satisfaction sub-dimension of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Additionally, it was determined that participants' scores from the sub-dimensions of using emotions and regulating emotions in the Emotional Intelligence Scale positively predicted the scores on the external satisfaction sub-dimension of the Minnesota Job Satisfaction Scale. Similar results were reported by Tram et al. (2016) and Boštjančič and Boštjančič (2017), indicating a positive relationship between emotional intelligence and job satisfaction. These studies highlight the importance of emotional intelligence in building positive relationships with employees and its impact on both internal and external job satisfaction levels. Similar findings regarding the relationship between cultural values and job satisfaction have been reported in studies like those by Petrides, Furnham, and Frederickson (2014) and Yuen et al. (2018).

In light of the findings of the study, it is important for businesses to recognize the impact of cultural values and emotional intelligence on employees' job satisfaction levels. This highlights the necessity for organizations to focus on teaching and developing emotional intelligence competencies, as such efforts can lead to increased job satisfaction. Additionally, evolving beliefs related to cultural values in a way that enhances job satisfaction can be beneficial for both the organization and its employees, ultimately leading to increased productivity.

The study has certain limitations. The impact of cultural values and emotional intelligence levels of private sector employees on job satisfaction was evaluated with a limited sample

group. This limitation is considered the most significant constraint of the research. Additionally, another limitation is that the findings in the study were obtained through a questionnaire consisting of four sections. It is assumed that individuals who participated in the study voluntarily answered the survey questions sincerely and genuinely.

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